

iPRES2019: “Eye on the Horizon”

Eye on CoreTrustSeal

Recommendations for Criterion R0 from Digital
Preservation and Research Data Management
Perspectives

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Agenda

- Introduction to CTS and R0
- Motivation for keeping an eye on CTS
- Our Data Basis
- Our findings on :
 - Designated Community
 - Repository Type
 - Level of Curation performed
- Conclusion

CoreTrustSeal - Overview

- Accepted trustworthy digital repository certification process for both, Research Data Management (RDM) and Digital Preservation (DP) communities
- De-facto standard for basic certification level
- Process based on self-assessment by applicants, reviewed by CTS, documented via publicly available assessment reports
- CTS reviewers evaluate answers and additional documentation against the requirements
- CTS consists of a catalogue of 16+ criteria (R1-R16) **including criterion R0** for background information about the applying repository

	Woods Hole Open Access Server (WHOAS) https://darchive.mblwhoilibrary.org/ CoreTrustSeal certification 2017-2019
	Woods Hole, MA 02543, USA
	Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research (ICPSR) https://www.icpsr.umich.edu/ CoreTrustSeal certification 2017-2019 WDS Regular Members
	330 Packard St, Ann Arbor, MI, USA
	LINDAT/CLARIN http://lindat.cz CoreTrustSeal certification 2017-2019
	Malostranské náměstí 25, Praha, Czech Republic
	World Glacier Monitoring Service, Zurich http://www.wgms.ch/ CoreTrustSeal certification 2017-2019 WDS Regular Members
	Dept of Geography, University of Zurich, Winterthurerstr. 190, Zurich 805
	Environmental Information Data Centre http://eidc.ceh.ac.uk/ CoreTrustSeal certification 2017-2019

Criterion R0 - *Background Information / Context*

Requirements

Background Information

Context

R0. Please provide context for your repository.

– *Repository Type*. Select all relevant types from:

- Domain or subject-based repository
- Institutional repository
- National repository system, including governmental
- Publication repository
- Library/Museum/Archives
- Research project repository
- Other (Please describe)

Brief Description of Repository

– *Brief Description of the Repository's Designated Community*

– *Level of Curation Performed*. Select all relevant types from:

- A. Content distributed as deposited
- B. Basic curation – e.g., brief checking, addition of basic metadata or documentation
- C. Enhanced curation – e.g., conversion to new formats, enhancement of documentation
- D. Data-level curation – as in C above, but with additional editing of deposited data for accuracy

Comments

– *Outsource Partners*. If applicable, please list them.

– *Other Relevant Information*

- R0 serves as a central characterization of the repository
- Outstanding role of R0 in CTS: no compliance level, important as other criteria explicitly refer to R0
- No equivalent context criteria in other certification processes (unique data basis)
- Mixture of standardized choices (e.g., Repository Type & Level of Curation) and free text items (e.g., Designated Community)

Motivation - CTS as a tool to self-reflect

Does CTS work as a tool to “self-reflect” on digital preservation activities?

→ requires: Understandability of R0

- Is there proof that Requirements have been understood?
- Are there current gaps and misunderstandings of R0?

Does CTS work as a tool to “self-reflect” where the community is at?

→ requires: Comparability of results

- Does CTS procedure lead to standardized and comparable answers concerning *Repository Type*, *Level of Curation*, and *Designated Community*?

Motivation - CTS Review Process

Our eye = a “digital preservation” view

68 CTS certified repositories, mostly from RDM field (CESSDA and CLARIN require CTS certification), some from cultural heritage / DP sector (e.g., National Archive of the Netherlands)

→ answers to *Repository Type*, *Level of Curation* and *Designated Community* suitable for RDM & DP comparison

Open call for CTS Review as a chance to update R0

→ requires: list of potential refinements for R0

- Which recommendations for R0 could lead to broader acceptance of CTS within the RDM and DP community?

Our Data Basis

Extracted and normalized Information from 40 assessment reports on:

- Brief Description of the Repository's Designated Community
- Repository Type (self-classification via checklist)
- Level of Curation Performed (self-classification via checklist)
→ see our Data Basis: <https://zenodo.org/record/3267690>

Analyzed CTS Supporting Information:

- Brief Guidance within the requirements themselves
- [Extended Guidance](#) with more detailed information for each requirement
- [CTS Glossary](#): definitions and terminology used in CTS

Experience with basic level certification

● Previously acquired seal ● No experience

Brief Description of Repository's Designated Community

<https://pixabay.com/de/photos/spielsteine-bunt-smilies-lustig-1744790/> CC0

Requirement: *“Please make sure that the response is specific”*

→ *Does the available Supporting Information help applicants describe their Designated Community?*

- OAIS definition of Designated Community (DC) in the Glossary
- One example for “specific” DC provided: *“quantitative social science researchers and instructors”*
- Terminology for specifying DC: *“A clear Designated Community demonstrates that the applicant understands the **scope, knowledge base, and methodologies** [...]”*

Designated Community - Data Basis Results

Use of CTS Terminology in R0's Designated Community section

- only 35 % use term “Designated Community”, others refer to “users” or “target communities”
- 10 % refer to “scope”
- only one institution (2,5 %) mentions the DC’s knowledge base
- 7,5 % describe DC’s methodologies
- 5 % explicitly refer to OAIS

Designated Community - Critical Analysis

- Overall, little appliance of CTS terminology
- Misleading Sub-Headline “**Repository’s** Designated Community”: According to OAIS, only an **Archive** can have a Designated Community
- Terms like “knowledge base”, “scope” and “methodologies” aren’t further described in Supporting Information
- Designated Community important (reference to 9 other CTS criteria), but differing answers suggest that Supporting Information on Designated Community is insufficient

Designated Community - Recommendations Made

Change sub-headline “Brief Description of Repository’s Designated Community”

Comment CTS Board decision: *“To avoid potential confusion, 'Repository' will be dropped from the sub-headline, and a definition of Repository added to the Glossary. The Requirements and Guidance will be checked for consistent use of 'Repository' versus 'Archive'.”*

ACCEPTED

Stimulate formalized Descriptions of Designated Community

Comment CTS Board decision: *“Explanations from the Extended Guidance will be moved into the Guidance, with revisions where necessary to stimulate more formalized descriptions of the Designated Community. We will consider providing an example description in the Extended Guidance.”*

ACCEPTED

Repository Type - Choices Given

1-n plus optional comment

- Domain or subject-based repository
- Institutional repository
- National repository system, including governmental
- Publication repository
- Library/Museum/Archives
- Research project repository
- Other

Image: duncan c "Type graffiti"
<https://www.flickr.com/photos/duncan/5040432390/> CC-BY-NC

Are choices self-explanatory?

e.g., Glossary definition for Publication repository: *Generic, multidisciplinary repository, focusing on data linked to publications.*

Repository Type - Data Basis Results

- 55% identify against only 1 type
- 15% against 2 types
- 5% against 5 types
- 1 “Other”:

“Mendeley Data is a generalist open research data repository, applicable to all areas of science”

52.5% added comments, further describing:

- domain content
- mission / history
- services provided

Distribution of *Repository Types* given in answer to R0

Repository Type - Critical Analysis: Definitions

... are we all on the same page?

What is a repository?

- A. "Your archive" in a technological sense
- B. "Your archive" in the OAIS sense

What is being certified?

- Boundaries of workflows?
- Is a trustworthy Repository a trustworthy Archive?
- Do we agree on what is being certified?
- Are we clear enough in our language?

Image: Micky Lindlar, CC-BY

Repository Type - Critical Analysis: Comments

*Domain or subject based repository: A domain-based repository with focus on **research data from social sciences**; **National repository system**, including governmental: **A national service resource for research and teaching**; **Library/Museum/Archives**: Social science **data archive***

(Comment from Self-Assessment Report R0 Repository Type section)

Depth: Intellectual content contained, limited to one or several specific subjects

Width: Audience (of authors and producers), e.g., project / institutional / national

Function: To archive, preserve; a resource for a specific group

Hard to understand what is being described due to mixture of depth/ width/ function

Repository Type - Recommendations Made

Define Repository's Boundaries

Comment CTS Board decision: *"The Glossary will be updated with a definition of the term 'Repository'"*

ACCEPTED

Replace mixture of depth, width and function with 3-level approach

Comment CTS Board decision: *"... [current list] has not been flagged by applicants as being inappropriate. Even more, there have been extremely few 'other' repository types proposed by applicants. Notwithstanding the above, **this topic is something we encourage the community to start a discussion on [...]**"*

DEFERRED
(Explored by
others)

Level of Curation - Choices Given

1-n plus optional comment

- A. Content distributed as deposited
- B. Basic curation - e.g., brief checking, addition of basic metadata or documentation
- C. Enhanced curation - e.g., conversion to new formats, enhancement of documentation
- D. Data-level curation - as in C above, but with additional editing of deposited data for accuracy

Supporting Information provided:

Changes made on copies only and in-line with producer-repository license agreements

Level of Curation - Data Basis Results

55% identify against 1 type only:

- most frequent stand-alone choice “Level D”
- no one identifies against “Content distributed as deposited” only
→ every institution performs at least Basic Curation

55% added comments, further describing:

- the applicability of different levels chosen
- the processes used for curation

Distribution of *Level of Curation* given in answer to CTS

R0

Level of Curation - Critical Analysis: Comments

Problem 1: Partial applicability resulting in inability to benchmark

Metadata on variable level is displayed in the online catalogue.

3 institutions talk about their Level D processes

*All transcript data is all converted [...]. In addition, **some data** is checked against linked audio data for accuracy.*

*Our staff review **all incoming data** files and apply **specialized curation activities such as quality assurance, file integrity checks, [...] and file transformations [...]**. We work closely with authors to ensure that the data is in a format and structure that best facilitates long-term access, discovery, and reuse.*

Problem 2: Different definitions of extent of processes associated

Level of Curation - Critical Analysis: Comments (2)

Risk of misinterpretations:

- Do we all define curation the same way
- Does curation contain all preservation activities?
- Does preservation contain all curation activities?

Level of Curation as is:

- Heavily focused on (descriptive?) metadata, documentation and data accuracy
- Lacks basic classification against preservation strategies (e.g., normalization, migration, emulation, redundant storage)
- Level of Curation != Level of Preservation

Image: Micky Lindlar, CC-BY

Level of Curation - Recommendations Made

Describe Conditions for Levels Applied

Comment CTS Board decision: *“A note will be added to the Extended Guidance to encourage applicants to add further details - for example, about the proportion of data in the collection curated to a certain level - in the case they selected more than one Level of Curation”*

Include Digital Preservation-centric Model

Comment CTS Board decision: *“The Guidance for R10 contains the question 'Is the level of responsibility for the preservation of each item understood?'. Some more detail and/or scenarios will be added to the Extended Guidance to illustrate where this may be relevant; for example, if depending on the size of an object, fewer redundant copies are made.”*

REJECTED

(PARTIALLY)
ACCEPTED

Our Conclusion

How does CTS fare between RDM and DP?

→ Concise definitions and examples in CTS Supporting Information could foster collective understanding and bridge gaps between RDM and DP communities

Comparability

→ Unclarity of terminology leads to differing answers, complicating benchmarking
→ Assessment reports good basis to check where the community “is at”

Reactions on our work so far

→ 10 recommendations for R0 review: 5 accepted, 2 partially accepted, 1 deferred and 2 rejected, → see [CoreTrust Review Feedback](#)

→ Data Basis: over 1.000 views & 170 downloads, → see <https://zenodo.org/record/3267690>

Thank you.
Questions? Comments!

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